

A photograph of a megalithic stone archway. The sun is shining brightly through the opening, creating a lens flare effect. The surrounding landscape is dark and silhouetted, with some trees visible in the background.

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volume **1**

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On the cover: Markov Kamak Sanctuary in Rila Mountain. Photo by Vasil Markov.

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THE MEGALITHIC COMPLEX OF REGO DA MURTA CONVERGENCES OF THE SACRED AND PROFANE, OF LIFE AND DEATH, IN THE RECENT PREHISTORIC LANDSCAPE OF CENTRAL PORTUGAL

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Abstract. This article investigates the ritual practices and beliefs associated with the Rego da Murta Megalithic Complex in Portugal, highlighting the intersection between the sacred and the profane. The monuments, such as dolmens and menhirs, functioned not only as burial sites but also as symbols of communal identity. The complex's location suggests its significance as a ritual centre, facilitating connections between communities and their surrounding landscapes. The study reveals the continuity of megalithic traditions, illustrating their adaptation to the region's social dynamics and emphasizing the importance of these monuments in fostering social cohesion and cultural expression within prehistoric societies.

Keywords: Megalithic complex, habitats, central Portugal

Introduction

The megalithic monuments analysed in this article are located in Alvaiázere, in a depression between the Nabão and Zêzere rivers, in the interior of central Portugal. In discussions about megalithism, we often assume a separation between the profane and the sacred. While useful for interpretation, this dichotomy may limit our understanding of the social and ritual dynamics of the communities that built and used these monuments. An approach that promotes a more comprehensive analysis of regional evidence could raise new questions and uncover behaviours directly or indirectly linking the realms of the living and the dead. This interrelationship suggests that megalithic practices could be deeply intertwined, where the distinction between the sacred and the profane is

not merely spatial but an expression of the beliefs and experiences of these societies. Such an integrative perspective is essential to comprehend the complexity of rituals, and the meanings attributed to the megalithic monuments, broadening our view of human interactions with the environment and the significance of these sites over time. Following this reasoning, the concept of 'dwelling' should be explored as a subjective experience reflecting the relationship between individuals and space, as highlighted by Peter King (2004), who stated that dwelling is something we all experience, but not in the same way. Therefore, landscape development must be seen as a cultural continuum involving architectures, actions, resources, and natural elements (Ingold, 2000; Thomas, 2006).

In analysing the Rego da Murta megalithic monuments, recognizing them as places of voluntary, often ritualized deposition over time, we must consider a series of attributes that go beyond the built structures, material culture, or recognized deposition contexts. It is crucial to understand their connection with the landscape and communities, visibility and intervisibility, durability, proximity to routes and water bodies, associations with artistic expressions or astronomic (Figueiredo et al., 2018), etc. This process involves a lengthy cognitive journey resulting in the creation of 'centres of meaning' within the landscape (Thomas, 2006). Thus, megalithic analysis should account not only for their physical characteristics but also for the meanings attributed to them over time, expanding our understanding of the interaction between human practices and the inhabited landscape, especially in relation to singular life spaces where people sleep, eat, and manage thought and action that characterize the behaviour of these groups.

The Rego da Murta megalithic complex

The Rego da Murta Megalithic Complex consists of 14 monuments, including dolmens, menhirs, atypical structures without funerary functions, and a rock art panel featuring cup-marks and connecting grooves (Figueiredo, 2007, 2010, 2013, 2017, 2019a, 2021). These monuments are located on a plain, forming an interface between

several ridges where evidence of occupation by these groups has been recorded.

The monuments cover an area no larger than 1.5 km², which must have been a sacred space, as all recorded acts appear interconnected by symbolic or ritual actions (Figueiredo, 2007). Among the archaeological sites, two dolmens have been fully excavated: Dolmen I and Dolmen II of Rego da Murta (Figueiredo, 2021, pp. 40–48).

Figure 1. A) Geological map representing the location of the Rego da Murta Megalithic Complex; B) Core of the Rego da Murta Megalithic Complex with indication of registered monuments 1. dolmen I, 2. dolmen II, 3. to 9. menhirs, 10. undetermined site, 11. slab with dimple rock engravings, 12. atypical site, 13. undetermined site. C) Satellite image with the location of the nucleus next to the Rego da Murta river. D) Dolmen I of Rego da Murta. E) Dolmen II of Rego da Murta.

Dolmen I is a corridor monument with a distinct architectural layout. The chamber is sub-polygonal in shape, composed of eight orthostats, and accessed via a significant slope between the corridor and the chamber. Excavation revealed signs of disturbance, complicating the separation of depositional layers. Despite these challenges, three main

depositional areas were identified: the centre of the chamber, the corridor entrance, and the area near orthostat C (Fig. 1). Circular structures within the site suggest the use of perishable materials, possibly as supports for furniture, as seen in European megalithic monuments (Midgley, 2005). Artifacts recovered include a variety of ceramics with four distinct decorative styles, flint lithics (such as blades, arrowheads, scrapers, and microliths), and polished stone tools, including axes and chisels. Additionally, items of personal adornment were found, such as pendants, necklace beads, and a bell-shaped conical button. Faunal remains indicate the presence of both domestic and wild animals. Funerary practices included inhumation and cremation, identified through anthropological analysis (Figueiredo et al., 2024). Radiocarbon dating indicates two main occupation periods: the Late Neolithic/Early Chalcolithic and the Late Chalcolithic/Early Bronze Age (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Table with the calibrated representation of the observed absolute dating's

Dolmen II (Fig. 1), located 400 meters to the north, features a polygonal chamber and an elongated horseshoe-shaped corridor, suggesting a fluid transition between these spaces. At least eight

collective ossuaries containing human and faunal remains were identified, along with various artifacts, including necklace beads, ceramic vessels, and lithics (Figueiredo, 2021). Absolute dating places these depositions in the 3rd millennium BCE (Fig. 2). Some human bones displayed signs of manipulation before their final deposition. The lithic assemblage includes hundreds of objects, primarily flakes, arrowheads, and adornments made from materials such as variscite, chrysoprase, schist, and quartzite. The ceramics exhibit diverse decorative patterns.

In addition to these two sites, the area includes a set of menhirs (Figueiredo, 2013), an atypical structure, and a slab with cup-marks (Figueiredo & Monteiro, 2018). Lithic remains, such as cores, and flakes made of chert, are scattered throughout the area (Figueiredo, 2007, 2010, 2017, 2019a, 2021).

Between sacred and everyday sites

The occupation of the territory in Alto Nabão during recent prehistory is a complex topic, marked by a scarcity of information, particularly related to settlements, as most data, except for the site of Castelo da Loureira (Figueiredo et al., 2014) and the settlement of Serra de Alvaiázere (Félix, 1999), comes from surveys. This limits a more coherent understanding of the relationship between habitats and practices associated with cults and rituals, especially concerning megalithism in the region. Even the sites that have undergone excavation have seen limited interventions, with only minor test pits conducted. However, a general analysis suggests a possible interrelationship between the ridges surrounding the core and the monuments of Rego da Murta. Most archaeological research has mainly focused on the study of caves and megalithic structures, and for the region of Alvaiázere, despite intensive surveys conducted in the municipality, only the Rego da Murta complex is known (Figueiredo, 2021).

Regarding the known habitats (Fig. 3–4), most of the sites, based on the collected artifact remains, date from the Final Neolithic to the Bronze Age. They are located on ridges or slopes, which allow for

extensive visual control of the landscape and potentially offer various defensive advantages. These locations suggest an adaptive strategy by the communities inhabiting the region that prioritized areas with visibility, especially for the periods when the highest number of practices and deposits have been recorded in the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta. Upon examining nearby sites, such as Relvas, Serra Mosqueiro, Castelo da Loureira, Forno do Cal, Penedos Altos, Sobral Chão, and Castelo da Ameixieira, it is noted that most are situated above 250 meters in altitude, except for Forno do Cal, which, despite being at 210 meters, has a steep slope providing visibility similar to that of the other sites (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Rego da Murta Complex Megalithic with the representation of habitats and caves existing nearby, relative to the deposits in the dolmens.

The site of Penedos Altos, reaching about 350 meters, is particularly interesting because some of the recovered material suggests a later occupation (Bronze Age), with similarities to those recorded in Serra de Alvaiázere (Félix, 1999), although other artifacts may be contemporary with the phase of occupation of the megalithic monuments.

The sites of Sobral Chão and Outeiro de São Pedro, on the other hand, present a collection that, despite having a larger quantity of Iron Age artifacts, also includes evidence of prehistoric occupation (Antunes, 1994, pp. 26–27; Silva, 1994, pp. 29–30), such as ceramic fragments that have analogies with materials found in Anta II of Rego da Murta (Figueiredo, 2007), dating from the 3rd millennium BC. In particular, the macrolithic stone industry made of quartzite stands out, including nuclei, large flakes, and points. This industry is consistent with findings from other sites in the region and has been associated by researchers studying the Zêzere, a neighboring area to Nabão, with Languedoc influences (Oosterbeek, 1997, p. 130; Cruz, 2010). Anta I of Vale da Laje, located in Zêzere, is one of the examples pointed out, having relevant interest for this article, as it is a megalithic monument. Other locations, such as the caves of Cadaval, Ossos, or Lapa da Furada, have also provided some specimens of this industry. It is noteworthy that these materials are relatively common in sites interpreted as habitats in the region of Alvaiázere, having also been recognized in Santa Margarida, in Tejo (Baptista, 2004), and in Maxial, located near Zêzere (Cruz & Oosterbeek, 1998), just to give a few examples.

If we consider that, based on the similarities with other artifacts, namely those designated as Languedocian, and that these objects are of Mesolithic tradition, without forcing their connection to the Paleolithic, we can mention that this material continuity suggests that local communities maintained similar cultural practices over different historical periods and a contemporary occupation, reflecting a continuous dialogue between past and present in local traditions and extending them to the megalithic monuments at the time of their adoption. These traces are especially visible in the most recent levels, with various elements recorded in the two dolmens of Rego da Murta, and are also evident in the dolmen of Azurrague, located in Ourém (Fig. 4), the megalithic monument closest to this complex.

The absolute dating of the contexts where macrolithics were found in Anta II of Rego da Murta, attributed to the Early/Middle Chalcolithic, and the study of the contexts of the Middle Neolithic in Anta I of Vale da Laje, as highlighted by Oosterbeek (1997), suggest that the deposition of these objects was linked to significant rituals, with

their importance recognized at specific moments. There is no synchronization of macrolithic deposits between the two monuments, according to the dates. Likewise, in Anta I of Rego da Murta, objects appear only at specific moments, possibly related to the last deposits of the first occupation (Final Neolithic/Early Chalcolithic). If we consider this fact, although the deposition of macrolithics is recorded in both dolmens of Rego da Murta, the specific reason for their association is unknown. However, their presence is evident in almost all habitat sites surrounding the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta.

Figure 4. Thematic map of the region, with representation of archaeological sites from recent prehistory mentioned in the article.

An exception is the site of Forno de Cal, further south and close to the Nabão River. This site stands out for its unique characteristics, lacking wall structures and macrolithics. The surveys conducted allowed for the observation of a set of artifacts that deviate from the patterns evidenced in the other sites. The low presence of quartzite tools, contrasting with the abundance of flint artifacts, suggests a functionality or chronology probably distinct for this space, which, however, in a superficial analysis, would also be integrated into the habitat typology.

The lack of detailed studies does not allow us to go further in the interpretation or relationship with the rest of the regional panorama. This difference may be related to various factors that have not yet been fully explored.

However, a bit further south, in the municipality of Ourém, we record the settlement of Agroal, excavated in the 1980s (Lillios, 1991), and the settlement of Fonte Quente (Cruz, 1997), located in the valley of the Nabão River, both also portrayed as open and unfortified sites, with a strong artifact component predominantly of plain ceramics. These two sites create a pattern of occupation that, together with the similar materials observed and dates that chronologically point to the Early Bronze Age (Fig. 2), lead us to integrate Forno de Cal into the same temporal framework. Given this observation, we do not agree with the assumption raised by Ana Rosa Cruz (2010, p. 41) that by the end of the Chalcolithic, the territory had ceased to be marked by funerary monuments and became characterized instead by stone-built settlements. In fact, we believe that new inhabited spaces could arise in the landscape, but without great relevance in the structuring of fortifications or the stone structuring of their dwellings, the latter being registered at least in Nabão in Agroal, Fonte Quente, and Forno de Cal.

Also, contrary to the researcher's model (idem, 2010, p. 41) that argues that at this time "the function of caves changes (although they are still used for the burial of high-status individuals); they are also used for episodic camping and permanent habitation, losing some symbolic importance," this assumption seems incorrect to us, due to the fact that we observe later, as recorded in the site of Algar da Água (Figueiredo, 2019b) and Algar da Malhada de Dentro (Fig. 2), the exhumation of human osteological remains, the first with datings extending to the Bronze Age and the second to the Late Iron Age. This latter case requires new datings for confirmation, as well as the recognition of the specific ritual of the deposits, since the data comes from mixed deposits of sediments, but where anthropologists recorded the presence of bones from several individuals, one of these bones was dated.

Excluding this latter site, although fundamental for understanding this issue, we can say that funerary rituals persisted at least until the Middle Bronze Age, with no current evidence of a schism

in these practices at the end of the Chalcolithic. It is also important to note that the only site recognized as a habitat in a cave is observed in the site of Ave Casta (with dates from the Chalcolithic into the Bronze Age), which is a cave, with a high roof and which opened along its entire lateral side to the outside, located very close to the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta. Occupations of Algar da Água (Figueiredo, 2019b) outside this funerary scope occur only in the Final Iron Age, where we register small occupations, probably opportunistic, by very small groups, probably shepherds, which extend with very similar characteristics into the Roman period. This cavity, during the Iron Age, also received symbolic artistic acts, being the westernmost cavity known as filiform art from this period (Figueiredo, 2019b; Figueiredo et al., 2023).

The pattern of distribution of archaeological sites around the complex of Rego da Murta suggests a strategic planning of territorial occupation, where the proximity between the spaces varies within a grid of 1.5 km to 3 km, indicating a strong cohesion among the prehistoric communities in the region. This spatial organization could have facilitated social interaction, communication, and the exchange of goods and ideas among groups, resulting in a dispersed yet interconnected settlement with a clear visual control of the fertile valleys of the Nabão and the transhumance routes. Comparisons with other regions, such as those along the Tejo and Zêzere rivers, reveal significant differences: while the sites in Alto Nabão appear to be more visually integrated, the steep terrain in the Zêzere has led to greater dispersion and isolation of settlements (Baptista, 2004; Cruz, 2020). These differences in spatial organization may reflect distinct social and economic strategies among the communities, highlighting the influence of geography on the formation of settlement practices and mobility.

A relevant aspect for analyzing the interconnection of the Megalithic Complex with the landscape lies in the strategic location of the Rego da Murta complex. The geology, terrain morphology, and slope lines indicate that this area, besides being crossed by an important tributary of the Nabão River, the Rego da Murta stream, is characterized by an open, flat landscape that facilitates easy mobility. This configuration would have promoted the movement and crossing of

groups, reinforcing the connectivity between the known prehistoric sites, which seem to have been established to control or supervise the surrounding space.

Since no other similar area is known nearby, a central question arises: was this space a unique symbolic core, intended to serve the ritual and symbolic needs of different dispersed small groups? Could this zone have functioned as a communal center shared by various communities in the vicinity? Its strategic location in an easily navigable area raises the hypothesis that the site's choice may have been deliberate, conveying important concepts, meanings, and messages to those who traversed the region, whether indigenous or foreign. It may have also served as a territorial marker, signifying belonging to a community or social/economic pacts between them, reinforcing its importance as a central point in the inhabited and ritualized landscape.

Its proximity to the Rego da Murta stream also suggests a symbolic or functional connection with water, which, besides being a source of life, could have played a ritual role. In this specific case, the stream overflows its course in winter, based on the sedimentary layers and pollen analysis results, and it is believed that such a situation would have been more pronounced in prehistory, making it particularly relevant for the reformulation of soils or symbolism of connection. The construction of the Rego da Murta dolmens over the ancient riverbed, which no longer flowed permanently at the time the monuments were erected, suggests a deliberate choice of location, possibly based on the symbolic value of water. This space also appears to have emerged during certain phases, as palynological analyses show that the sediments from the contexts appear very washed (Figueiredo, 2007).

In the specific case of the Rego da Murta II Dolmen, the presence of an atrium at the end of the corridor adds another layer of interpretation (Figueiredo, 2010). The configuration of the atrium could suggest a symbolic function related to controlling the entry of water into the monument. This architectural detail strengthens the hypothesis that water, even when not flowing permanently, continued to play a fundamental role in the conception and use of these funerary spaces. If we examine the cores of Jogada, Vale de Chãos, or Vale da Laje, located to the east, they are also connected, being situated near the Zêzere River,

but without any possibility of direct relationship to submersion due to the steep terrain of the river valleys.

Final considerations

The occupation of the Alto Nabão territory during recent Prehistory, where the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta is located, appears to have been shaped by geographical factors and marked by a significant interconnection between habitats and sacred spaces. Given the absence of another similar nucleus in the region, it is plausible that this area held shared meanings for the various groups that inhabited it. The spatial distribution of the habitat sites reveals a dispersed yet interconnected settlement pattern, strategically situated in elevated areas or slopes that provided broad visual control over the surrounding landscape. The relationship between these habitats and the megalithic monuments indicates territorial and social cohesion, with the sites occupying prominent locations, likely not only for ease of mobility but also for their central role in the ritual and symbolic practices of these communities.

The location of the habitats in elevated areas would have enabled these communities to exercise control over local resources, such as the stream, while maintaining a symbolic connection with the megalithic monuments. These monuments may have functioned as ceremonial centers, communal meeting points, and markers of territorial identity. The Rego da Murta nucleus stands out as a focal point in this network of interconnections, both for its strategic geographic position and its symbolic function. Its location in a flat and easily accessible area, near the Rego da Murta stream, may have facilitated movement and contact between groups, contributing to its prolonged use over time.

The proximity of the nucleus to water raises further hypotheses about the role of this resource in the rituals and beliefs of the local communities. Beyond its practical utility, water likely held a significant spiritual meaning and served as a crucial means of circulation and transport. In the absence of organized roads or land routes, rivers provided the most efficient and accessible connections between communities and regions.

In regions like Alto Nabão, where rivers and their tributaries permeate the landscape, it is likely that the proximity of settlements to these watercourses facilitated not only social interaction and trade but also the exchange of ideas, beliefs, and cultural practices.

An important question is the role of this nucleus as a communal space, possibly shared by multiple dispersed communities in the region. Given the scarcity of similar nuclei in the area, the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta may have functioned as a center for symbolic and ceremonial convergence, playing a central role in maintaining the social and ritual networks among neighboring communities.

The absence of significant defensive structures at some archaeological sites suggests that, while communities had defensive concerns, visual control and mobility were likely more relevant than physical fortifications. This reinforces the idea of a shared, connected landscape. Other sites, such as the Castle of Loureira, with fortified structures, show a chronology that surpasses the occupation of the megalithic monuments. This dating does not closely align with the construction of the wall, and it can be hypothesized that it might predate the fortification. Further data is needed to confirm these interpretations.

The continuity observed in occupation patterns, such as the persistence of quartzite lithic industry associated with the Mesolithic, supports the hypothesis that local communities maintained cultural traditions over long periods, absorbing new influences while retaining elements of previous practices. The presence of similar lithic and ceramic materials in both habitats and funerary contexts, such as the dolmens of Rego da Murta and the caves, suggests an intersection between the everyday and the symbolic. The megalithic monuments seem to have been integrated into the systems of belief and social practices of these communities.

In conclusion, the archaeological landscape of Alto Nabão, centered around the Megalithic Complex of Rego da Murta, appears to have been shaped by a complex network of interactions between habitats and megalithic monuments. This pattern of occupation reflects not only an efficient territorial organization but also a ritualized landscape, where geography, natural resources, and cultural traditions played key roles in constructing the identity and social cohesion of prehistoric communities.

Future research may provide further insights into the dynamics between inhabited and ritual spaces, enriching our understanding of the recent Prehistory of the central region of Portugal, near the Nabão River.

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